

Study of the Sapogenins from *Trigonella corniculata*, Linn.

I. P. Varshney and A. R. Sood

The seeds of *Trigonella corniculata*, Linn. yields three steroidal sapogenins in the form of saponins. One of the sapogenins present in 70% yield of the total genins has been identified as yuccagenin in addition to diosgenin already reported. The third sapogenin is present in traces only.

Trigonella corniculata, Linn. locally known as "Kasturi Methi" belongs to the family Leguminosae, sub-family Papilionaseae. The seeds of the other species *Trigonella foenum-graecum*, Linn., have been reported to contain diosgenin, gitogenin and tigogenin by Marker *et al.*¹, while Mme. Heitz² and Varshney and Sharma³ have reported the presence of only two genins, diosgenin and gitogenin. Recently Varshney and Sood⁴ reported the presence of diosgenin in *Trigonella corniculata* seeds in about 25% of the total genins, present in the seeds.

The seeds of *Trigonella corniculata* obtained from the local market of Indore were well defatted with petroleum ether and then exhausted with ethanol. The recovery of the extract gave a gummy brown mass which was first extracted with petroleum ether followed by extraction with ether and acetone.

The alcoholic extract left after extraction with the above solvents gave all the tests for steroidal saponins. The thin layer chromatography of the saponins on silica gel showed it to be a mixture of three products which could not be separated.

The mixture of saponins was hydrolysed with sulphuric acid and the sapogenins extracted with ether/petroleum ether mixture. This gave a mixture of sapogenins which on paper chromatography and TLC showed the presence of three genins. The mixture of sapogenins was chromatographed on alumina which separated the three products, one major in about 70 percent and the second in 25 percent yield of the total sapogenins. The third is present in traces only. The two products present in quantity were purified by rechromatography. One of the products present in twentyfive per cent yield has earlier⁴ been identified as diosgenin. The other sapogenin present in 70 per cent yield has m.p. 238-40 (cf. yuccagenin m.p. 242-43), (Found : C, 74.59; H, 9.81%; Calcd. for C₂₇H₄₂O₄; C, 75.3; H, 9.7%). It gave an acetate m.p. 173-76 (cf. yuccagenin acetate m.p. 178). (Found : C, 72.66; H, 9.1%; Calcd. for C₃₁H₄₆O₆; C, 72.3; H, 9.0%).

1. R. E. Marker, *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2242.
2. Mme. S. Heitz, *Compt. rend.*, 1959, **248**, 283.
3. I. P. Varshney and S. C. Sharma, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 564.
4. I. P. Varshney and A. R. Sood, (in the press).

Both the genin and acetate gave yellow colour with tetranitromethane which showed the presence of carbon-carbon double bond. The physical constants of the second genin and acetate are in quite agreement with yuccagenin. The genin has been identified as yuccagenin by mixed melting point, I.R. spectra and TLC with an authentic sample of yuccagenin.

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Department of Chemistry,
Shri Govindram Seksaria Technological Institute,
Indore-3.

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